

Experimental and numerical investigation of the structural behavior of cold-formed steel built-up box sections

M. Banu Priya*,✉ and Aarthi Karmegam**

✉ Email: banupriyaap17@gces.edu.in

*Government College of Engineering, Srirangam, Trichy - 620 012, INDIA.

**Government College of Engineering, Bodinayakkanur, Theni - 625 582, INDIA.

In Cold-Formed Steel (CFS) construction, built-up box sections are becoming more and more common for beam members. This paper presents a thorough analysis of the experimental and numerical aspects of the innovative face-to-face joined built-up cold-formed steel beams. It is done by finding buckling-moment resistance capacity under four-point bending. Two press-braked channel pieces are used to build these built-up beams, and bolted connections hold them together. The two different cross sections examined in the research work are namely HT (face-to-face connected hollow CFS channel section having screws only at the top) and HTB (face-to-face connected Hollow CFS channel section having screws both at the top and the bottom). The beam is square in cross-section and contains stiffener only at the web portion. The study took into account three distinct parameters: (1) screw spacing; (2) the screw's placement; and (3) the thickness of the section. A total of 8 specimens were tested using the experimental method. Here, the load-displacement relationship and the failure mechanism are covered in detail. Using Finite-Element (FE) models produced with the commercial software ABAQUS, numerical analysis was performed. Regarding ultimate moment capacities and buckling modes, the findings of the actual tests and the FE agreed rather well. The FE models were therefore confirmed. The design strengths computed concerning the American Iron and Steel Institute (AISI) were compared with the design strengths found through experimental and FE method. Also, a detailed discussion is provided on how the parameters as mentioned earlier affect stiffness, buckling resistance behavior, flexural strength, and the failure mode. After a discussion of the experimental, theoretical, and FE results, the ideal screw spacing, location, and specimen thickness are suggested.

KEYWORDS: Screw configuration; section thickness; structural stiffness; load-deflection behavior; failure modes; finite element analysis.

The use of Cold-Formed Steel (CFS) structural components in the building industry has significantly grown in recent decades. The utilization of these built-up CFS components is growing more prevalent in numerous other countries, as well as in North America, Europe, and Australia. CFS beams are less capable of bearing moments because of their open profiles and thin walls, which can lead to complex buckling failure modes and associated issues with stability. Furthermore, the lack of torsional stiffness limits the open-form CFS beams. In recent years, built-up CFS parts have evolved to solve these problems. Generally, open

parts are joined or fastened together to create built-up sections. These novel built-up sections are necessary when a CFS section is not strong enough to handle the design stresses, particularly when the beam's depth is restricted¹. These are quickly replacing cold-formed steel structural components as the next generation, offering creative and effective new solutions.

The primary focus in the design of built-up sections is to evaluate the influence of partial composite action. A complete composite action is obtained if two component elements are welded along the full length, where the adjoining edges of the webs undergo the